

I.FAST

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DELIVERABLE REPORT

CONSTRUCTION OF THE XLS ACCELERATING STRUCTURE PROTOTYPE

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ABSTRACT

The objective of I.FAST Task 7.5 was to build and test two prototypes of the X-band (12 GHz) accelerating structure designed for the CompactLight (XLS) project, a new class of linac-driven FEL facility (<https://www.compactlight.eu/>).

This document reports on the work carried out within the project, with an analysis of the production process for the fabrication of the two accelerating structures, RF tests and validation of the full prototype.

I.FAST Consortium, 2025

For more information on IFAST, its partners and contributors please see <https://ifast-project.eu/>

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Executive summary

The CompactLight acceleration structure allows compact, normal-conducting accelerators to run at high repetition rates (up to kHz), which benefits physics and biomedical applications. These accelerators, particularly photon sources based on Inverse Compton Scattering (ICS), are increasingly valued for their small size, lower cost, and tunable monochromatic X-ray output used in diagnostic imaging and related fields.

This report describes the successful design and production of 12 GHz (X-band) accelerating structure prototypes for the CompactLight (XLS) project. The fabrication process and RF measurements supported the design's validity. Strengths included reliable RF engineering, accurate simulations, quality machining, and useful brazing tests. Issues such as cell stacking, assembly, braze jig performance, unstable oven temperatures, and copper expansion were identified for future improvement.

1. Introduction

CompactLight was a Design Study [1] funded by the European Union under the Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme, completed in 2021, with the design of an innovative, compact, and cost-effective hard X-ray FEL facility, using the most advanced technologies developed for accelerator components, <https://www.compactlight.eu/>.

The CompactLight acceleration structure has been designed to provide a key component for very compact normal conducting accelerators capable of operating at high repetition rates, up to kHz regime [2].

These accelerators have a wide range of applications, from basic physics to biomedical applications, i.e. photon sources based on Inverse Compton Scattering (ICS), that can be considered a fundamental tool for high-resolution diagnostic imaging.

Currently, the scientific interest in these sources is rapidly growing due to their reduced size and costs, compared to their capabilities as a “tunable monochromatic X-ray source” for use in Mammography, K-edge imaging, phase-contrast imaging.....

Aspects that have a significant social impact, with economic benefits for all the community.

The CompactLight acceleration structure enables compact, normal-conducting accelerators to operate at high repetition rates (up to kHz). These accelerators are useful in physics and biomedical applications, especially photon sources based on Inverse Compton Scattering (ICS), which are essential for high-resolution diagnostic imaging. Interest in these sources is increasing due to their small size, lower cost, and use as tunable monochromatic X-ray sources for mammography, K-edge, and phase-contrast imaging—all with significant social and economic benefits.

2. CompactLight accelerating structures construction analysis

The construction of the first two CompactLight acceleration structures was carried out in several phases:

- a. RF design evaluation
- b. Cooling system design and thermal stabilization
- c. Preparation of technical drawings for construction
- d. Precision machining of cells
- e. Brazing tests (few cells)
- f. Brazing of the whole accelerating structures
- g. Vacuum tests and RF characterization

We did not experience any significant problem with the evaluation of the RF design of the structure and the development of the engineering drawings, including the design of the thermal stabilization system. Additionally, the precision machining of all the elementary cells proceeded very successfully, achieving a high level of quality, accuracy, and reliability in production. Most of the brazing tests, which were carried out on a limited number of cells (3-5), were also completed without notable issues.

Therefore, most activities were carried out without problems (a, b, c, d, e), achieving the expected results within the planned timeframe, while others encountered some difficulties (f, g), which caused delays and non-conformities, giving at the same time important clues how to improve the brazing process for the entire structure. Most of these issues were related to the construction of the pre-prototype, which was completed almost one year late.

A detailed description of the work-flow steps for the design and the high precision mono-parts production of the two X-band structures has already been reported in the I.FAST DEL 7.5: “Construction of the XLS accelerating structure pre-prototype” [3].

2.1 Elementary cells fabrication

VDL ETG was responsible for fabricating all the elementary cells of the X-band structures.

All the cells were machined using an ultra-high-precision manufacturing process, with strict mechanical tolerances ($\leq 2\ \mu\text{m}$ precision and $\leq 25\text{nm}$ roughness, which results in mirror-like surfaces), that has not required any additional RF tuning of the cells after production.

All the elementary cells of the structure (composed of two half cells) were individually controlled via metrology and RF frequency measurements. Keeping the metrology results as reference, the frequency measurements have a systematic error of roughly 150 kHz i.e. one micron between the two halves, and a random error of one micron or less.

The typical work-flow for the cells production is reported below:

1. Production of starting material
2. Pre-machining
3. Thermal annealing
4. Final-machining
5. Cells metrology control
6. Cleaning
7. Packaging

At the end of the manufacturing process, given the fragile nature of all the parts, especially in the centre zone with RF functionality, the packaging of all the individual discs was crucial for their subsequent handling/shipping to other partners for further processing. This was done using special membrane boxes, see Figures 1a,1b,1c1,d.

This procedure has proven to be very reliable and has not caused any problems.

Figure 1a: Elementary cell in membrane box

Figure 1b: End cover in membrane box

Figure 1c: RF couplers in membrane boxes

Figure 1d: All the cells of the second accelerating structure in membrane boxes

2.2 Cells metrology

At the end of the manufacturing phase, all the disks have been measured at VDL, to verify their compliance with design values and to ensure their quality before the brazing process.

Figure 2 shows the reference system used for the measurements.

Figure 2: Reference system for metrology

The following four pages contain the values measured (42 points) on the first disk of the accelerating structure No.2. A total of 108 disks were measured and characterized [4].

All the values were within tolerance, on the range of 1-micron deviation or below that value, meeting the requirements for a good assembly process and RF performance.

This demonstrates that the precision machining of all elementary cells has been highly successful, achieving a high level of quality, accuracy, and reliability in terms of production.

All the measurements have later been confirmed also by CERN metrology.

ZEISS CALYPSO

7.6.1204

Progr name	131-89021-lfast Xband disk 001	Company	VDL ETG Precision bv
Drawing number	131-89021		Hurksestraat 13
Order number	852486-906925		5652 AH Eindhoven
Part ident	lfast Xband Disk 001-2	Telefoon	+31 (0)40 2638209
CMM-Type	PRISMO_ULTRA		
Operator	Marco		

No. measured values 42
No. values: red ● 0

Name	Measured value	Nominal value	+Tol	-Tol	Deviation +/-

Points 14
Filter type Geen filter
Lc
upr
Vmess[mm/sec]
Probe radius 0,7502
Evaluation method Minimum-zone element

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Points 21
Filter type Geen filter
Lc
upr
Vmess[mm/sec]
Probe radius 0,7502
Evaluation method Minimum-zone element

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Perpendicularity Ref_B to Ref_A.Y	-0,0005	0,0000			-0,0005
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Perpendicularity Ref_B to Ref_A.Z	0,0001	0,0000			0,0001
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ZEISS CALYPSO
7.6.1204

Part name
Order number
Part ident

131-89021-Ifast Xband disk 001
852486-906925
Ifast Xband Disk 001-2

Name	Measured value	Nominal value	+Tol	-Tol	Deviation +/-
Concentricity 69,9975 to Ref_A-B.Y	0,0002	0,0000			0,0002
Concentricity 69,9975 to Ref_A-B.Z	0,0006	0,0000			0,0006
// Parallelism flat 4,001 on side ref_A	0,0011	0,0000	0,0020	0,0000	0,0011
Distance 12,3230	12,3222	12,3230			-0,0008
// Parallelism flat 12,3230 to ref_A	0,0013	0,0000	0,0020	0,0000	0,0013
Position distance 8,3320.X	8,3305	8,3320	0,0015	-0,0015	-0,0015
// Parallelism flat 8,3320 to ref_A	0,0017	0,0000	0,0020	0,0000	0,0017

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7.6.1204

Part name
Order number
Part ident

131-89021-Ifast Xband disk 001
852486-906925
Ifast Xband Disk 001-2

Name	Measured value	Nominal value	+Tol	-Tol	Deviation +/-
Concentricity 70,0025 to Ref_A-B.Y	0,0001	0,0000			0,0001
Concentricity 70,0025 to Ref_A-B.Z	-0,0005	0,0000			-0,0005
Points 60 Filter type Geen filter Lc Vmess[mm/sec] Probe radius 0,7502 Evaluation method normVecDev Best Fit Translation Rotation X 0,0000 0,0000 Y 0,0000 0,0000 Z 0,0000 0,0000					
DIN Lineform on side ref_A.x	7,3210	7,3202			0,0009
DIN Lineform on side ref_A.y	0,0000	0,0000			0,0000
DIN Lineform on side ref_A.z	-4,8758	-4,8753			-0,0004

ZEISS CALYPSO
7.6.1204

Part name **131-89021-Ifast Xband disk 001**
Order number 852486-906925
Part ident Ifast Xband Disk 001-2

Name	Measured value	Nominal value	+Tol	-Tol	Deviation +/-
DIN Lineform opposite ref_A	0,0028	0,0000	0,0030	0,0000	0,0028

Points 60
Filter type Geen filter
Lc
Vmess[mm/sec]
Probe radius 0,7502
Evaluation method normVecDev

Best Fit
Translation Rotation
X 0,0000 0,0000
Y 0,0000 0,0000
Z 0,0000 0,0000

DIN Lineform opposite ref_A.x	9,0016	9,0028			-0,0013
DIN Lineform opposite ref_A.y	0,0000	0,0000			0,0000
DIN Lineform opposite ref_A.z	-4,8760	-4,8753			-0,0006
DIN Lineform total	0,0028	0,0000	0,0030	0,0000	0,0028

Points 120
Filter type Geen filter
Lc
Vmess[mm/sec]
Probe radius 0,7502
Evaluation method normVecDev

Best Fit
Translation Rotation
X 0,0000 0,0000
Y 0,0000 0,0000
Z 0,0000 0,0000

DIN Lineform total.x	9,0016	9,0028			-0,0013
DIN Lineform total.y	0,0000	0,0000			0,0000
DIN Lineform total.z	-4,8760	-4,8753			-0,0006

2.3 Pre-prototype brazing

CPI TMD was responsible for the brazing of the XLS accelerating structure pre-prototype. As part of their work, they provided input into the structure design to enable optimal assembly and brazing, they determined the braze type and quantity to be used, and they designed and manufactured the jig required for construction and braze of the prototype structure.

This activity proved to be rather problematic, contributing to mechanical and vacuum issues, as well as delays, in completing the various phases of the project.

The main problems we had were:

- i. vacuum leaks on RF couplers cooling pipes and flanges (Figure 3a, 3b,3c), that forced us to revise their design and brazing method and to launch the production of two new couplers;
- ii. the assembly of the entire structure before brazing (stacking of all the cells) and the use of the braze jig for lifting and rotating the whole structure for brazing;
- iii. The brazing process, the instability of the oven temperature and an inadequate compensation for copper expansion inside the jig during the brazing cycle.

2.3.1 Mechanical and vacuum tests: problems experienced

After brazing the structure showed:

- a. large vacuum leaks coming from some of the braze channel vent holes (see Figure 3);
- b. a mechanical deformation on the wall of the first RF coupler (see Figure 4);

c. the dimensional check showed 203 measurement points out of tolerance and the structure's axis revealed a clear "banana shape", with a maximum deviation in the middle of up to 0.42 mm (almost 100 times higher than expected, see Figure 5 a, b).

For more details see [4]: I.FAST DEL 7.5: "Construction of the XLS accelerating structure pre-prototype".

Figure 3: Vacuum leaks from vent holes

Figure 4: Mechanical deformation of the first RF coupler

Figure 5a: Accelerating structure with coordinate system under measurement

Figure 5b: Structure's axis with a clear "banana shape"

After the pre-prototype brazing, a careful analysis of the processes and methods used for brazing the pre-prototype, the effectiveness of the assigned roles, as well as the unexpected events occurred, led us to implement the necessary corrective actions for the second structure.

2.4 Pre-prototype RF characterization

Despite the problems encountered during the brazing process, the RF measurements performed on the pre-prototype after brazing, see Figure 6, provided results very close to those expected [5].

Figure 6: Pre-prototype after brazing

In addition to the S-parameters measurements already reported in the I.FAST DEL 7.5, the electric field profile on the axis and the phase advance per cell were measured, with a motorized bead-pull setup, see Figures 7a and 7b.

Figure 7a: Bead-pull setup for E_z measurement

Figure 7b: Nylon wire at the structure RF input

The measurements were taken using a 110 GHz, Rodhe & Schwarz vector network analyzer (VNA), with a four-port calibration, with a center frequency of 11.994 GHz, 300 MHz span and 1 kHz IF bandwidth.

Figure 8 shows the bead-pulling results with a plot of the electric field on axis (E_z) in arbitrary units. The plot compares the measured E_z component (red curve) compared to the one simulated with CST Microwave Studio (blue curve).

The field seem to be very tapered with peaks quite aligned to the simulation.

Figure 8: Bead-pull Ez measurements (in blu CST simulation, in red Ez measured)

Figure

The structure was designed to have a cell-to-cell RF phase advance of 120° . Figure 9 reports the deviation of the cell-to-cell phase advance from the nominal value. The maximum deviation is within one degree.

Figure 9: Cell-to-cell phase shifts variations with respect to the design one (120°)

Figure 10 shows the RF power reflected at the input and output of the structure.

Figure 10: Input and output reflected power

3. Brazing of the second accelerating structure (full prototype brazing)

After an accurate evaluation of the problems encountered for brazing the first accelerating structure (the pre-prototype), and a careful analysis of the improvements required, in order to minimize the risk of failures, we have decided to braze the second accelerating structure (the prototype) at Paul Scherrer Institute (PSI-Zurich).

PSI is an I.FAST partner with a proven experience in brazing accelerating structures.

They have successfully brazed the 104 C-band structures (@ 5.712 GHz) for the Swiss FEL, and have also developed special procedures and equipment for handling these components, maintaining high accuracy during staking and vacuum brazing.

3.1 Change in brazing strategy and Paul Scherrer Institute (PSI) involvement

After long negotiations, PSI agreed to braze the structure. To cover the brazing costs, we received support from CERN, through the AWAKE (Advanced Wakefield Experiment), which requested to use the CompactLight accelerating structure built by the I.FAST collaboration.

AWAKE is the world's first proton-driven plasma wake field acceleration experiment and has demonstrated the acceleration of electrons to several GeV's in its first Run [6]. The goal of Run2 is acceleration of a witness bunch whilst preserving emittance and energy spread [7].

AWAKE generates high gradient plasma wake fields using a long proton bunch by seeded self-modulation in a long plasma cell. A second electron beam is injected into the following plasma cell to be accelerated by the wake fields of the modulated proton bunch. This witness beam is externally injected from a dedicated injector which consists of an S-band RF-gun and X-band bunching and acceleration systems. Details on the acceleration scheme can be found in [8, 9].

The RF design of X-band accelerating structure has been done in the framework of the CompactLight design study and is therefore very similar to the IFAST accelerating structure. AWAKE needs three high-gradient X-band accelerating structures and one bunching structure.

The IFAST structure built by the IFAST collaboration will be used as one of the accelerating structures for the above-described plasma wake field acceleration experiment.

3.2. PSI brazing phases

All the parts of the second structure have been shipped from CERN to PSI in October 2025. The brazing of the structure had been scheduled for mid-November 2025, but in order to complete a thorough inspection of all the cells and carry out preliminary RF tests on groups of cells, it has been scheduled in January 2026.

The brazing process will involve several phases [10]:

3.2.1. Inspection

All single parts have been inspected and checked for cleanliness and damages.

Thanks to the membrane boxes used during transport, this task was completed successfully, ensuring that all parts arrived clean and undamaged.

3.2.2. Preparation of work

PSI has one smaller oven (for brazing diameters up to 400mm) and one bigger oven (for diameters up to 800mm and height of 3000mm). The first brazing cycle involves the RF couplers, using a brazing alloy with a high melting point, such as it does not melt again in the further brazing steps.

For the XLS structure, it is planned to first braze the two RF couplers (input and output). This means the ConFlat flange + Cover + Coupler + Cooling Pipes, for the input side and the output side of the structure.

The WR90 flange with the waveguide is mostly brazed separately because it would need separate tooling to hold everything. But that is decided once the coupler pieces are stacked.

At the end of this phase, both ends of the structure are brazed and ready to be brazed onto the structure. However, before being stacked on the structure, they are first checked with a leak test to verify their vacuum tightness (leak rate $<10^{-10}$ mbar l/sec).

At the same time, the brazing alloy is placed in the two circular braze grooves of each disk, ensuring it is ready for brazing.

3.2.3. Stack assembly procedure

The structure will be brazed in an upright position, ensuring that all the disks in the stack are perfectly aligned.

Starting with the first RF coupler, all the disks must be mounted and aligned on a very stable baseplate, adding one disk after the other, using a “shrink-fit” assembly technique.

Due to their strict mechanical tolerances, each disk is warmed up and/or cooled down depending on whether it needs to expand or shrink.

The disk to be added to the stack is about 30°C warmer than the disks already in the stack, and it has an increased inner diameter. Once added to the stack, it cools down to the stack temperature and reaches its final self-centring position.

When all disks are stacked, the second RF coupler is placed on top of the structure. All the stacking is done manually with a handling tool.

After stacking all the disks, including the two RF couplers, some bars, which not distort while heating, are mounted to fix the stacked components for brazing.

The completely stacked structure then goes into the oven in an upright position. During heat-up, the copper expands and that movement must not be restricted.

3.2.4. Mechanical testing

After brazing, with the structure still in the vertical position, a leak test of the structure and a pressure test with nitrogen, for the cooling channels, are done. Another leak test is performed after the pressure test to ensure that there were no problems during the pressure test.

In case of a leak, it is possible to re-braze the structure by adding additional brazing filler to the specific location.

3.2.5. RF testing

After mechanical testing, with the structure still in a vertical position, the wire with the motorized bead-pull measurements is fixed.

The structure is then rotated through 90 degrees, using a special lifting device with a rotation arm, for its RF characterization.

The following measurements are taken:

- the phase advance per cell;
- the Q value;
- the frequency error per cell (with respect to the nominal one);
- the reflected and transmitted power at nominal frequency.

3.2.6. Expected work completion

It is planned to complete the work on the structure brazed, including the vacuum tests and its RF characterization, in about one month, by end of January 2026.

4. TRL and MRL achieved and future perspectives

Most of the activities carried out for Task 7.5 are technically mature and have already been proven to be fully reliable at an industrial level.

These can be assessed with a TRL/MRL of at least 7.

In particular:

- The EM codes currently available for the RF design of a structure (i.e. CST Microwave Studio) are highly reliable, and have provided the operating parameters with great accuracy. This has eliminated the need of correction tools or frequency tuners on the structure.
- The production process for cells is well established and does not present any particular risks. Micron-precision machining have ensured high levels of reliability and precision.

Currently, the most-risky activities and bottlenecks in the entire construction process are those related to brazing techniques. These can be assessed with a TRL/MRL of 6 or lower. The entire process still requires further developments, studies and testing.

5. Conclusions

Construction of the CompactLight accelerating structure prototypes has been completed. The brazing and RF testing of the second prototype will be finished in about a month, in January 2026.

The manufacturing process, which was carried out in several phases, highlighted the strengths and weaknesses of the currently available technology.

In particular, the activities that did not encounter any significant issues were:

- ✓ the RF design and the development of engineering drawings for the structure. The simulation codes currently available for component design have proven to be highly reliable;
- ✓ the precision machining of all the elementary cells was very successful, achieving a high level of quality, accuracy and reliability in term of production;
- ✓ Most of the brazing tests, carried out on a reduced number of cells (3-5), have provided important insights for future improvement.

Conversely, the activities that proved to be somewhat problematic contributing to the mechanical and vacuum issues encountered for the prototype construction, were:

- the stacking of cells and assembly of the entire structure, as well as the braze jig, used for secure rotation and lifting of the fully assembled structure prior to brazing;
- the brazing process, the instability of the oven temperature, and the inadequate compensation for copper expansion inside the jig during the brazing cycle.

It will be crucial in the future to identify and fully assess these problems in order to make the necessary improvements.

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